

EDUCATION AND CULTURE

THE DESIGN AND EVALUATION FOR INTERACTIVE ANIMATIONS TO IMPROVE TRADITIONAL CULTURE LEARNING FOR CHINESE PRESCHOOL STUDENTS

Jingyue Zhang

Naresuan University, Thailand.
Email: jingyuez65@nu.ac.th

Chayanis Chuenchaichon

Naresuan University, Thailand.
Email: chayanisc@nu.ac.th

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study examines the effectiveness of the application of interactive animation to preschool students' learning of traditional culture, focusing on the role of interactive animation in stimulating students' interest and promoting their understanding of traditional cultural knowledge. **Method:** Quantitative research methods were used to collect test data from 4-5 years old kindergarteners in the middle class through whole cluster sampling. The data collection tools included: Learning Competency Evaluation Sheet and Satisfaction Questionnaire for parents, preschool students, and teachers. **Result:** The results show that children are inclined to cartoon characters with high saturated colors, and are favor of animal-type characters than human-type characters, especially large-eyed and oval-shaped animals, and the exaggerated actions with the characters can easily bring children into the plot. Children are more sensitive to fast-paced music, and the guidance sound effects have increased children's interactivity when the branching storyline. During interaction, children prefer simple touch-based controls such as tapping and dragging. Meanwhile, the interactive animation learning intervention significantly improved students' grades in the traditional culture, and positive evaluations from parents and teachers further confirmed that interactive animation has great potential for application. **Significance:** The effectiveness of interactive animation on traditional culture curriculum is verified through empirical data, providing a design framework for interactive animation that suits the cognitive development of Chinese preschool students, filling the gap between interactive animation and traditional culture curriculum in a new integration method, suitable for popularization and use in different countries and cultural, and providing domestic and foreign educators with teaching strategies to improve the teaching effect.

KEY WORDS

Interactive Animation, Preschool Students, Traditional Culture, Learning Skills.

INTRODUCTION

Interactive animation is closely related to the continuous expansion of new media evolving forms. Interactive animation as a new media form that integrates visual, sound, plot and interactive elements, which has attracted attention from preschool education and has gradually become a tool of educational media. Interactive Children's Education Market Forecast 2021-2026 (Research and Markets, 2021) shows that the global interactive children's education content market is growing at an average annual rate of 10.2%. Especially in the Asia-Pacific region. China Children's Digital Content White Paper 2021 (iResearch, 2021) found that the proportion of children aged 3-6 who watch animation programs or APPs with interactive features has reached 73%. With the rapid popularization of interactive animation in preschool education, interactive animation has an impact on children's thinking about learning.

Numerous empirical studies have demonstrated that interactive animation can provide preschool students with a lively, immersive, and active learning experience (Aslan et al., 2022). Interactive animation engages children's visual, auditory, and tactile sensory systems through interactive elements, and deepens experiential understanding of knowledge by direct linking actions to information (Figure 1). Neumann and Neumann (2014) mentioned in their journal published in 2014 that children showed stronger learning engagement and emotional involvement in interactive touch-based contexts. After learning, students' memory for sequential types of knowledge was significantly improved.

Figure 1: Demonstration of Interactive Animation Information Transfer, Based on Bai (2023).

In practice, interactive animation is widely used in a variety of preschool disciplines such as math, English, science, and language cognition (Rachmavita, 2020). Joint statement issued by NAEYC-FRC (2012) stated that when technology and interactive media are used intentionally and appropriately, they are effective tools for supporting children's learning and development.

Interactive animation has shown rich content and diverse forms of development in preschool education in China, but still faces problems, which include a significant gap between design concepts and educational functions (Zeng, 2018). In China, interactive animation lacks awareness of design principles; the few children's educational interactive design lacked the complex interactive mechanism to guide children's cognitive transfer, cause-and-effect reasoning, or problem-solving (Wang, 2019). In essence, it is still a "passive receptive" learning media. In addition, some designs focus on superficial forms such as images, characters and colors (Ren, 2022), ignoring children's psychological and cognitive developmental laws, which makes children's interactive animation lack of constructive meaning "deep interaction", interactive animation does not play a real role.

Chinese traditional culture curriculum in recent years has become more and more highly concerned by the education sector, and infiltrating traditional culture curriculum into early childhood preschool education can promote the healthy growth of young children (Niu, 2025). In 2017, the State Council of the Communist Party of China (CPC) issued "However, due to the deep history, complex context and abstract symbols of traditional culture, how to effectively transform traditional culture into visual content suitable for the cognitive level of children aged 3-6 still lacks mature paradigms and theoretical support. Therefore, by combining traditional culture curriculum with interactive animation, the researchers hope to provide a design framework of interactive animation for preschool students learning traditional culture curriculum. The research centers on the adaptability of this interactive animation to preschool students, Entertainment value of the interactive animation, and the actual teaching effect of the interactive animation. These answered the question of how to enhance preschool students' traditional culture learning skills through interactive animation. The objectives of the study were:

1. To design interactive animations to enhance preschool students' traditional culture learning skills.
2. To evaluate related satisfaction with the design of interactive animations.

This study developed a framework for designing interactive animations suitable for preschool students to learn about traditional culture, and explore the role of interactive animations in promoting children's cognitive development and cultural awareness. The design framework integrates multinational interactive animation

design experiences and cultural expressions to provide a practical approach for domestic and international educators, policymakers, and designers to fill the theoretical gaps in the field of related research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human–Computer Interaction (HCI) and Cognitive Strategies for Children’s Learning Skills

Human-computer interaction (HCI) has become a key component in the current development of digital technologies, especially in virtual scenarios that emphasize user experience and emotional expression. According to the “cognitive psychology of HCI”, HCI systems are able to recognize and respond to user emotions (Gupta, Ahuja, & Garg, 2022). It has been observed that when users are actively involved in the interaction process, they exhibit higher levels of satisfaction and loyalty (Zheng, Xiao, & Zhou, 2024).

In this context, the emotional connection between children and machines is thought to stem from early children’s intuitive experience of social behavior, verbal communication, and social emotions, which are gradually simulated by technology in multimodal interactions to stimulate social cognition in children’s interacting machines (Rohlfing et al., 2022). Alam (2022) proposes a model that describes the early stages of a child’s interaction with a social robot interaction development in stages, which provides theoretical support for understanding the evolution of children’s emotions and human-machine relationships. Research has shown that children exhibit greater attention, motivation to imitate, and exploratory behavior when they engage in emotional feedback with machines (Zhang, Breazeal, & Park, 2023).

According to Piaget’s theory of cognitive development (Piaget, 1952), children between the ages of 3-6 are in the “preoperational stage”, in which children can express their thoughts through symbols such as words, images and actions. Children’s human-computer interaction (CCI) systems well-suited to provide highly symbolic and figurative interaction objects for children in the “Pre-processing Stage”. Among these, the linguistic system within CCI has also been shown to help children formulate thought processes that promote the development of linguistic symbols and expressive skills (Ale, Sturdee, & Rubegni, 2022). When children interact with the virtual characters within the interaction, they ascribe a certain “character” identity to the machine, leading to deep emotional connections and cognitive transfer.

Panpsychism is one of the early cognitive characteristics of children proposed by Piaget. Panpsychism is the tendency of children in the pre-computational stage to perceive non-living objects as having subjective consciousness. In CCI, this panpsychism tendency is not weakened, but is further activated by the development of interactive devices. It is this cognitive tendency that makes children more willing to trust machines and establish a psychological foundation. Meanwhile, Vygotsky’s theory of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) further reveals the possibility of children’s “learning transfer” in human-computer interaction, which refers to the range of tasks that can be accomplished by children with the help of their skills. It represents a potential space for cognitive growth (Vygotsky, 1978), and it has been shown that the ZPD provides a dynamic, personalized feedback mechanism in CCI, which can promote the development of children’s cognitive and linguistic skills (Bodrova & Leong, 2024).

Interactive Animation Design for Kindergarten Children

The use of digital media for teaching and learning in kindergarten has become the norm. However, not all interactive animations are appropriate for preschool students. Research has shown that the design of elements in interactive animation has a significant impact on children’s cognitive, emotional and behavioral development (Chen, 2022). In this context, the design of interactive animation must consider not only the instructional goals but also the cognitive developmental characteristics and aesthetic preferences of children (Li & Wang, 2022). However, according to our research and study on the interactive animation market, we found that most of the interactive animations generally have problems such as fragmented content structure and incoherent context. For example, some interactive animations, despite their educational intent, lack systematic instructional design and narrative structure, which undermines children’s sense of engagement and learning outcomes

In interactive animation, visual, auditory and tactile senses are considered as three important elements, Lin in 2020 meticulously categorized interactive animation into storyline, character, color, music and sound (Lin, 2020), followed by theories in 2021 suggesting that the integration of the touch element in interactive animation plays a Role of Touch Element. In order to realize a better integration of the research results, the researchers combed through the research theories of several scholars and provided a comprehensive design framework (Table 1), based on the division of interactive

animation elements, children’s age and children’s cognitive dimensions (perception, attention, thinking skills) (Piaget, 1952), to explore the appropriate

interaction methods and their cognitive support paths for children of various stages. Interactions and their cognitive support pathways.

Table 1: Table of Summary Children’s Interaction Types and Cognitive Development Support Pathways.

Interaction Elements	Perception ■ Attention ● Thinking Skills ▲				References
	Age 3-4	Cognitive Skill Applicable	Age 5-7	Cognitive Skill Applicable	
Plot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repetition • Cause and Effect 	▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploration • Tasks 	▲	Fan et al.,2021
Character	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Round/Ellipse • Passive 	●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triangle, Square • Active 	●	Calvert,2020 Lillard et al.,2015
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple Props • Props follow the Plot 	▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex Props • Props Upgrade 	▲	
Color	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Colors 	●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distinguish between Distinct Color Luminance 	●	Ji et al.,2025 Hou & Huang,2017
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived Emotional Warmth 	■	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceive Complex Emotions 	■	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obvious Psychological Implied 	▲	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obvious Psychological Implied 	▲	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Brightness 	●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Brightness 	●	
Music and Sound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive Music 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognizing Music 		Wang,2018
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expressing Emotions 	■	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expressing Emotions 	■	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of Sound 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided by Sound Effects 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound Effects should not be too Long 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound Effects should not be too Long 		
Touch Element	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click • Drag 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Click • Drag • Slide • Rotate 		Li et al.,2022

Study of Traditional Culture Curriculum and Interest in Chinese Kindergartens

According to current kindergarten education planning, the curriculum for preschool students aged 3-4 and those aged 5-6 differ significantly. The 3-4 years old preschool students focusing on reading and basic literacy, whereas 5-6 years old children emphasize on creative expression. Against this background, teachers in kindergartens organize a variety of activities, including art-based learning, parental parenting education, picture book reading, and interactive play experiences. These interactions have been shown to effectively improve learning skills. However, the shallow content of the curriculum and the lack of interactivity in the curriculum affect the effectiveness of curriculum implementation (Sun, 2025b). Furthermore, results from a 2022 sample survey indicate that “games and interactive experiences” are the most favored learning formats among children, suggesting that highly interactive and contextualized teaching and learning experiences can drive children’s interest in learning.

In study on traditional cultural elements, It is widely recognized that children are more receptive to and interested in cultural content that is vivid in imagery, entertaining, and offers strong opportunities for participation (Sun, 2025a). According to the current Chinese children’s animation click rate of traditional culture (By 2022), the top three animation genres preferred by children are myths and legends,

traditional festivals, and non-heritage skills, which are equipped with distinctive colors and exaggerated shapes. Additionally, the study found that children’s awareness of and interest in traditional festivals is significantly higher than that of other forms of culture. In particular, in some special activities, their motivation and emotional engagement were significantly higher (Zhao, 2023).

In the Chinese context, interactive animation featuring traditional culture often emphasize stylized or ritualized actions. For example, in the Chinese New Year theme, action patterns such as “paying homage to the New Year”, “lion dancing”, and “setting off firecrackers” have been effectively utilized, forming a kind of visual inertia for cultural recognition (Li, 2013). Studies have shown that stylized actions help children understand the logic of the story, identify character traits, and build memory associations (Piaget, 1952). Therefore, it is necessary to incorporate stylized actions into the design of interactive animation. Which can help enhance children’s learning outcomes and stimulate perceptual and emotional responses.

The Application of Interactive Animation in International Kindergarten Cultural Curriculum

An increasing number of countries are placing greater emphasis on preserving local culture through interactive animations during the preschool education stage. In Japan and South Korea, the

plot of interactive animations emphasizes early cultural exposure and behavioral mimicry, with a preference for gamified interactive experiences in their design, such as experiencing “seasonal rituals” in a virtual environment (Kim et al., 2018). In contrast, interactive animations in Nordic countries like Finland, focus on content construction and aesthetic experiences in visuals. These works typically use fairy tale structures and open-ended interactions to stimulate children’s emotional engagement and imagination, with cultural transmission being more implicit. For example, the interactive animation series “Moominvalley”, produced in Finland, is a representative work of Nordic interactive animation design concepts. Countries like the US and Canada emphasize children’s participatory and exploratory interactions, proposing “non-linear exploration” and “interactive narrative” in plot (Kabir, 2013), with a focus on “task-driven” approaches.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used quantitative research methods to design interactive animations based on traditional festivals and implemented them in actual kindergarten teaching to evaluate the impact of interactive animations on preschool students’ traditional culture learning skills. The study used preliminary interviews and literature to identify children’s areas of interest in traditional culture and teaching content. It also used learning competency evaluation sheet, satisfaction questionnaires for preschool students, parents, and teachers to evaluate the role of interactive animations in promoting preschool students’ traditional culture learning skills.

Subjects and Samples

The experimental group consisted of N=20 children from the middle class of HongYuan Kindergarten in Zhengzhou City, Henan Province, selected through cluster sampling. Among them, there were 10 boys and 10 girls, with ages ranging from aged 4-5. Two teachers participated in the teaching process, and 20 parents were also included in the satisfaction assessment. All participants and parents signed informed consent forms, and the study was approved by the kindergarten. The research project and all questionnaire materials were approved by the Naresuan University Institutional Review Board, with approval number No. P2-0370/2567.

Research Plan

The study lasted for three weeks, with three interactive animation teaching activities organized

around the themes of: Spring Festival, The Mid-Autumn Festival, and Laba Rice Porridge Festival. Each activity lasted 25 minutes. The animation content was presented through visual, auditory, and tactile interactions. The learning competency evaluation sheet was completed before the first lesson and after the last lesson, and the satisfaction questionnaire was distributed after the teaching was completed. Teachers assisted the children in filling out the questionnaires, and the parent and teacher questionnaires were collected in paper form.

Research Tools

The “Learning Competency Evaluation Sheet” was developed by the researchers in accordance with the standards of the “Learning Guidelines for Traditional Chinese Culture Curriculum for aged 3-6”, and contained 15 questions, including “Understanding of Festivals”, “Identifying Traditional Customs”, “Reciting Idioms”, etc. It was scored by a combination of observation and questioning.

The “Satisfaction Questionnaire” included surveys on the satisfaction of preschool students, parents and teachers. The children’s satisfaction questionnaire included subjective feelings such as interest in animation, interactive experience and learning gains. The parent satisfaction questionnaire included the evaluation of learning effects and pedagogical appropriateness. The teacher satisfaction questionnaire covered classroom interaction and instructional technology development, and a comprehensive tri-party evaluation. All three questionnaires adopted a five-point Likert scale for scoring.

Data Collection and Analysis

All data were statistically analyzed using SPSS 26.0 software. Paired sample T-tests were used to compare children’s pre- and post-test grades to determine whether the interactive animation was effective in improving learning skills. Satisfaction data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, covered means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions, to present the overall evaluation of the interactive animation by preschool students, parents, and teachers. The significance level was set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

1. Research objective 1: To design interactive animations to enhance preschool students traditional culture learning skills.

(1) Figure 2 shows the structure of the interactive animation plot, which is based on the themes of the

Spring Festival, The Mid-Autumn Festival, and Laba Rice Porridge Festival. The main storyline focuses on clearly describing the story, with interactive elements added after each plot point. When setting up the interactive elements, the approach drew on

American practices in interactive animation that emphasizes children’s exploration and interaction strategies, presenting branching storylines in a “task-based” manner to stimulate children’s thinking skills and increase their interest in participating.

Figure 2: Interactive Animated Plot Structure.

(2) Researchers designed three characters (Figure 3) for design, named “Pudgy Rabbit,” “Sister Luna,” and “Lucky Rat.” The characters were visualized through anthropomorphic and exaggerated animation designs. The characters “Pudgy Rabbit” and “Lucky Rat” adopted flexible and variable oval shapes, which suited the design principles in Table 1. In addition to improving children’s attention, these characters were also suitable for comical roles. “Sister Luna” adopted a square

shape, which gave the character a stable and reliable feeling. The character’s movements are also embedded with “behavioral imitation” from Japanese interactive animation, such as the characters performing “New Year greeting rituals” and “moon appreciation, which are stylized actions that suit Chinese festivals. The plot setting adds positive factors, such as the characters “encouraging” children to think and actively promoting the development of the plot.

Figure 3: Interactive Animated Character Visualization.

(3) In terms of color selection, high-brightness colors were employed to narrate the plot, while low-brightness colors were used for interactive games, complemented by warm and harmonious

accent colors to enhance children’s perceptual skills (Table 1). Given children’s innate cognitive tendencies toward color (Maule, Skelton, & Franklin, 2023), this study adopted context-

appropriate color strategies in theme design: the “Spring Festival” theme uses warm colors (Figure 4) to emphasize the festive atmosphere, “the Mid-Autumn Festival” theme employs cool colors (Figure 5) to convey an artistic conception, and the “Laba Rice Porridge Festival” theme utilizes low-luminance colors (Figure 6) to grounded in daily life. Due to children’s varying sensitivity to color, the design of scenes incorporates a mix of

colors, such as red lanterns complementing deep green pine trees, or a deep blue sky paired with a bright yellow moon, to avoid reducing children’s attention span due to excessive use of cool or warm colors. This design concept, which integrates color with scenario construction, aligns with the principles of Nordic countries that prioritize content development and visual aesthetic experiences.

Spring Festival Interactive Animation Color Scheme

Figure 4: “Spring Festival” Color Card.

The Mid-Autumn Festival Interactive Animation Color Scheme

Figure 5: “The Mid-Autumn Festival” Color Card.

Laba Rice Porridge Festival Interactive Animation Color Scheme

Figure 6: “Laba Rice Porridge Festival” Color Card.

(4) Figure 7 shows the interactive animation music design flowchart. When operating interactive animation media, select light, rhythmically strong music with narration. The narration is delivered by characters, replacing children’s emotional expressions to resonate with them. Set corresponding sound effects based on differences in interactive plots. When children trigger actions, sound effects provide real-time feedback and emotional guidance. Based on the theory in

Table 1, when setting sound effects to convey information, the correct and incorrect buttons have different dwell times. Long sounds are used to indicate rewards, while short sounds are used for errors. During interactive gameplay, the background music does not stop but continues to stimulate children’s auditory senses; however, the volume is reduced to provide children with space for cognitive reflection.

Figure 7: Interactive Music Flowchart.

(5) In addition to basic click and drag interactions, touch elements also include swipe, pinch, and rotate

gestures. Selecting appropriate touch elements based on different storylines enhances guidance

for children. Furthermore, the standardized button setup (Figure 8) before the start of interactive

games reinforces children’s learning mechanisms.

Figure 8: Interactive Touch Button.

2. Research objective 2: To evaluate related satisfaction with the design of interactive animations.

(1) Pre-test and post-test numerical measurements were analyzed using a paired-samples T-test, which included: festival knowledge comprehension (e.g., “Can you name a festival custom?”), custom recognition (e.g., “Can you correctly match festivals with traditional items?”), idiom story recitation (e.g., “Can you explain the meaning of an idiom story?”) and an open-ended questions assessing imaginative thinking (e.g., “Which cartoon plot impressed you the most?”). Composite scores were calculated for all indicators before and after the

intervention.

According to the scatter plot comparison of pre- and post-test results (Figure 9), the pre-test mean score was $M=27.14$ [SD: 4.8], and the post-test mean score was $M=31.35$ [SD: 5.1], with a significant overall improvement in mean scores [MD=+4.21, SE=1.11]. The difference was statistically significant [T=6.47], indicating that students demonstrated improved learning outcomes in traditional cultural knowledge through the use of interactive animation [$p: 3.35 \times 10^{-6}$, significant at $p<0.05$].

Figure 9: Comparison of Pre- test and Post-test Scores.

(2) According to the preference ratings for visual elements of among students in the experimental group, children showed a significantly higher preference for cartoon characters in high-saturation warm colors compared to low-saturation cool colors [High-saturation: $M: 4.35$, $SD: 0.58$; Low-saturation: $M: 3.60$, $SD: 0.72$; $t(19) = 3.42$, $p < 0.0028$, $d = 0.77$]. Character preference statistics across three interactive animation clips revealed that students generally favored animal-type characters with round eyes and oval shapes, whereas human-type characters received lower preference scores. Among all, the animal character “Pudgy Rabbit” was the most favored, with children even mimicking its exaggerated actions and dialogue after class.

- Pudgy Rabbit: Prop.%=50, Pref.n=10, M:4.45, SD:0.52

- Sister Luna: Prop.%=20, Pref.n=4, M:3.70, SD:0.65
- Lucky Rat: Prop.%=30, Pref.n=6, M:4.10, SD:0.60

Children also demonstrated differentiated preferences for rhythmic, informational/scientific, and experiential. Results showed a significantly higher preference for rhythmic sound effects [Prop.%=55, Pref.n=11, M:4.50, SD:0.56].

Lastly, the effectiveness of various touch interactions-tapping, dragging, and rotating-in sustaining children’s engagement was evaluated based on four dimensions: attractiveness, attention, sustained participation, and exploratory motivation.

- Tapping: received the highest engagement score [$EI = 4.45$], indicating strong interest and sustained involvement.

- Dragging: scored slightly lower [EI = 4.10], but showed high levels of attention and exploratory behavior.
- Rotating: [EI = 3.50], triggered curiosity but was observed to reduce focus over time due to complexity.

(3) A questionnaire survey was conducted among preschool students, parents, and teachers to evaluate satisfaction level with the experimental outcomes. According to the results, in the parental assessment dimension (Table 2), the item "Interest Stimulation" received a relatively high score [$\bar{x}=4.30$, $SD=0.47$], while "Family Interaction" scored lower [$\bar{x}=3.90$, $SD=0.62$], indicating that interactive animations still have room for improvement in promoting parent-child collaborative learning. Student satisfaction (Table 3) was generally high, particularly in "Interesting" [$\bar{x}=4.45$, $SD=0.45$] and Liked" [$\bar{x}=4.40$, $SD=0.48$], demonstrating that interactive animation was highly effective in engaging children's interest and emotional involvement.

In the teacher evaluation dimension (Table 4), "Applicability of Educational Content" was rated positively [$\bar{x}=4.20$, $SD=0.44$], suggesting that teachers recognize the educational value of the interactive animation. However, "Integration and Utilization of Resources" received a relatively lower score [$\bar{x}=3.95$, $SD=0.55$], indicating that optimization is needed in this area. The strong willingness of all three group to continue using the interactive animation, demonstrates the potential for further development of it. Results of parent's satisfaction questionnaire analysis (N=20)

Table 2: Parents Satisfaction Questionnaire Results.

Evaluation Dimensions	\bar{x}	SD
Learning Effect	4.12	0.53
Interest Stimulation	4.30	0.47
Family Interaction	3.90	0.62
Educational Resources	4.05	0.49
Personalized Learning	4.00	0.55
Subsequent Use	4.22	0.41

Results of preschool student's satisfaction questionnaire analysis (N=20)

Table 3: Preschool Students Satisfaction Questionnaire Results.

Evaluation Dimensions	\bar{x}	SD
Liked	4.40	0.48
Interesting	4.45	0.45
Learning Benefits	4.15	0.58
Characters and Stories	4.28	0.51
Interactive experience	4.32	0.46
Subsequent Use	4.35	0.43

Results of teacher's satisfaction questionnaire analysis (N=10)

Table 4: Teachers Satisfaction Questionnaire Results.

Evaluation Dimensions	\bar{x}	SD
Teaching Effectiveness	4.10	0.49
Learning Interest Stimulation	4.05	0.52
Interactivity	4.12	0.50
Applicability of Educational Content	4.20	0.44
Achievement of Educational Goals	4.00	0.51
Effectiveness of Technology-Assisted Teaching	4.18	0.47
Integration and Utilization of Resources	3.95	0.55
Subsequent Use	4.08	0.46

DISCUSSION

Studies have shown that interactive animations play a positive role in enhancing preschool students' interest and initiative in learning traditional culture. By optimizing the design of interactive elements and presenting traditional cultural content in an interactive format, their learning motivation can be stimulated. As noted by Li, Wang and Luo (2024) and Agustina et al. (2023), highly interactive digital technologies can enhance children's engagement and emotional involvement, thereby strengthening the immersion and sustainability of the learning experience. In the design, the study incorporated design principles from other countries-such as game-based mechanisms, character behavior imitation strategies, and aesthetic-oriented content construction-to ensure that the interactive animation aligns with children's cognitive development levels while also maintaining educational adaptability in cross-cultural contexts.

Visual symbols of traditional culture are presented through contextualized content, guiding students to acquire knowledge within specific cultural scenarios. This approach enhances children's culture perception and memory by transforming abstract knowledge into concrete imagery, thereby improving the effectiveness of cultural knowledge expression. Those finding are consistent with those of Minalla, A. A. (2024), who concluded that contextualized visual representations can assist young children in better understanding abstract concepts. In the study, the "scaffolding" support theory (Vygotsky, 1978) was used to set up design "problem-based". Techniques such as "character prompts", "voice guidance", and "feedback mechanisms" were employed to provide timely support to children during the learning process. This theory has been confirmed in studies by Raslan (2024), Ismail et al. (2023), and Stern and Hertel (2022), all of which demonstrate that scaffolding supports the internalize learning strategies and improve children's problem-solving skills.

Furthermore, the findings of this study align with those of Arifin et al. (2023), who used interactive devices to improve children's object recognition skills. Their experimental results indicated that interactive

technology had a positive effect on children's knowledge construction in early childhood education, and children were satisfied with their experience using such interactive tools.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This study involved the design of interactive animations based on the traditional Chinese culture curriculum and conducted a satisfaction assessment. The findings confirmed the effectiveness of interactive animations in teaching traditional Chinese culture to preschool students and demonstrated their potential for cross-cultural education. First, interactive animations tailored to children's cognitive characteristics, such as clear narrative structures, repetition and reinforcement, and interactive feedback mechanisms that can significantly enhance preschool students' interest and engagement in learning. Additionally, experimental results show a statistically significant improvement in students' performance before and after using the interactive animation. Satisfaction surveys also indicated a high level of acceptance and approval among the students.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed:

1. Curriculum content can be further deepened and diversified by introducing more cultural themes, such as mythological stories and traditional crafts, to enrich the representation of traditional culture.
2. In subsequent interactive animation applications, mechanisms for parent and teacher collaboration can be integrated to help children achieve a continuous learning experience.
3. In subsequent design and implementation, expand the design framework to validate its adaptability and expression paradigm across different cultural contexts.

Looking ahead, we suggest that with the advancement of interactive animation technology, it can be integrated with Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) to enable a "virtual-physical interaction" experience. Such an approach would support deeply integrates of cross-cultural, educational, and technological dimensions, thereby offering more innovative pathways to explore the applicability of education and cultural learning strategies.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. One limitation of this study is that there was the limited number of participants, due to its experimental nature that requires close control of many factors that affect the generalizability of the results to a wider population. However, the data

obtained are valuable as preliminary data for future research that may use a larger sample size. Moreover, this study was conducted in only one kindergarten in Zhengzhou City, which presents limitations in terms of geographical scope and representativeness of the sample. When extending the findings to kindergartens in other regions, differences in cultural backgrounds, educational resources, and learning habits may influence the effectiveness of the intervention.

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